

1. Raw Images

- Area Code: Contains the necessary Matlab codes for processing the raw fingerpad images and displays the results. A separate readme file is available in this folder to guide the user.
- Sliding Condition: Contains the raw images of the fingerpad for subjects 1 and 2 for sliding in radial and ulnar directions. Each folder of sliding direction (ulnar, radial) contains four sub-folders for each rotation angle (0, 15, 30, and 45 degrees). Each folder of rotation angle contains 3 sub-folders for the fingerpad images collected under the normal forces of 0.5, 1, and 1.5 N.

Below is the hierarchy and naming convention used for the folders storing the data:

- S1
 - Radial
 - 0Deg
 - ❖ Half N
 - ❖ One N
 - ❖ OneHalf N
 - 15Deg
 - ❖ Half N
 - ❖ One N
 - ❖ OneHalf N
 - 30Deg
 - ❖ Half N
 - ❖ One N
 - ❖ OneHalf N
 - 45Deg
 - ❖ Half N
 - ❖ One N
 - ❖ OneHalf N
 - Ulnar
 - 0Deg
 - ❖ Half N
 - ❖ One N
 - ❖ OneHalf N
 - 15Deg
 - ❖ Half N
 - ❖ One N
 - ❖ OneHalf N
 - 30Deg
 - ❖ Half N
 - ❖ One N
 - ❖ OneHalf N
 - 45Deg
 - ❖ Half N
 - ❖ One N
 - ❖ OneHalf N
- S2
 - Radial
 - 0Deg
 - ❖ Half N

- ❖ One N
 - ❖ OneHalf N
 - 15Deg
 - ❖ Half N
 - ❖ One N
 - ❖ OneHalf N
 - 30Deg
 - ❖ Half N
 - ❖ One N
 - ❖ OneHalf N
 - 45Deg
 - ❖ Half N
 - ❖ One N
 - ❖ OneHalf N
- Ulnar
 - 0Deg
 - ❖ Half N
 - ❖ One N
 - ❖ OneHalf N
 - 15Deg
 - ❖ Half N
 - ❖ One N
 - ❖ OneHalf N
 - 30Deg
 - ❖ Half N
 - ❖ One N
 - ❖ OneHalf N
 - 45Deg
 - ❖ Half N
 - ❖ One N
 - ❖ OneHalf N

- Stationary Condition: Contains the raw images of the fingerpad for subjects 1 and 2 for stationary condition (normal loading alone). Each folder of subject contains four sub-folders for each rotation angle (0, 15, 30, and 45 degrees). Each folder of rotation angle contains 3 sub-folders for the fingerpad images collected in three separate sessions.

- S1
 - 0Deg
 - Session1
 - Session2
 - Session3
 - 15Deg
 - Session1
 - Session2
 - Session3
 - 30Deg
 - Session1
 - Session2
 - Session3
 - 45Deg

- Session1
- Session2
- Session3
- S2
 - 0Deg
 - Session1
 - Session2
 - Session3
 - 15Deg
 - Session1
 - Session2
 - Session3
 - 30Deg
 - Session1
 - Session2
 - Session3
 - 45Deg
 - Session1
 - Session2
 - Session3

2. **Sliding Condition:** Contains a Matlab code titled “main.m” and other necessary “*.mat” data files to generate the following plots:

3. Stationary Condition: Contains a Matlab code titled “main.m” and other necessary functions and “*.mat” data files to generate the following plots:

